

THE KHOREZM EXPEDITION PHENOMENON: HISTORIOGRAPHY, SCIENTIFIC SCHOOL AND METHODOLOGICAL TRANSFORMATION (1991–2025)

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the historiography, scientific school, and methodological transformation of the Khorezm archaeological-ethnographic expedition (KAEE) from 1991 to 2024, emphasizing its development as an independent object of scholarly inquiry in post-independence Uzbekistan. Although studies of the expedition originated during the Soviet period, systematic reinterpretation became particularly active after independence, when national history, ethnogenesis, and cultural heritage were reconsidered beyond ideological frameworks. The study proposes a three-stage periodization of post-independence scholarship: the formative stage of ethnographic historiography (1991-1998), the stage of conceptual reinterpretation (1998-2016), and the contemporary stage (from 2016 onward), characterized by heritage-oriented and identity-based approaches. The first stage reflects the continuation of S.P. Tolstov's paradigm, in which KAEE findings were largely accepted as authoritative. The second stage marks a shift toward critical reassessment through new theoretical perspectives, influenced by state cultural policies, UNESCO initiatives, and major commemorative events related to Khorezm's historical legacy. The third stage corresponds to the reforms of the "New Uzbekistan" era, when the expedition's legacy began to be examined in relation to cultural heritage preservation, tourism, ethno-integration, and national identity.*

Keywords: *Khorezm archaeological-ethnographic expedition, S.P. Tolstov, Historiography, Khorezm, Methodological transformation, Cultural Heritage, National identity, Karakalpakstan.*

INTRODUCTION

The Khorezm archaeological-ethnographic expedition (KAEE), founded in 1937 under the leadership of Sergey Pavlovich Tolstov, occupies a central place in the development of archaeology and ethnography in Central Asia. For several decades, the expedition conducted large-scale archaeological and ethnographic research in the Khorezm oasis and adjacent regions, producing an extensive corpus of field materials, archival documents, photographs, and theoretical interpretations. These works significantly shaped scholarly understandings of ancient statehood, irrigation civilization, social organization, and cultural traditions of the peoples of Khorezm and Karakalpakstan.

During the Soviet period, the KAEE functioned not only as a research project but also as a powerful scientific school that established its own methodological principles, interdisciplinary approaches, and academic networks. Tolstov's theoretical concept of Khorezm as a center of ancient irrigated civilization and a crossroads of sedentary and semi-nomadic cultures became a dominant paradigm in regional studies. However, the ideological framework of Soviet historiography limited critical reflection on the political, institutional, and epistemological dimensions of the expedition's activities.

After the independence of Uzbekistan in 1991, the reinterpretation of national history, ethnogenesis, and cultural heritage created new opportunities to reassess the legacy of the KAEE. Scholars increasingly began to view the expedition not only as a source of empirical data but also as a historical phenomenon shaped by specific political, social, and intellectual contexts. This shift encouraged the emergence of new methodological approaches that emphasized historiography, heritage studies, identity construction, and the relationship between science and state policy.

Despite the growing body of literature, the KAEE has rarely been analyzed as an independent historiographical object across different historical stages. Most studies focus on particular findings or themes rather than examining the expedition as a coherent scientific school with its own internal evolution. Therefore, this article aims to analyze the transformation of the KAEE's historiography from 1991 to 2024, identify key methodological shifts, and demonstrate how changing political and cultural contexts influenced scholarly interpretations of the expedition's legacy.

METHODS

This study adopts a qualitative and historiographical research design to examine the scientific legacy and methodological transformation of the Khorezm archaeological-ethnographic expedition (KAEE) between 1991 and 2024. The research is based on a systematic review of scholarly sources, including monographs, journal articles, dissertations, archival materials, and conference proceedings produced in Uzbekistan and abroad.

The primary analytical approach is historiographical analysis, which enables the identification of dominant research paradigms, theoretical frameworks, and interpretive trends across different historical stages. This method is complemented by comparative analysis, allowing the study to trace continuities and shifts in scholarly interpretations over time. To enhance analytical depth, problem-based and chronological analysis were applied to reconstruct the development of the KAEE and its reception within academic discourse. Source criticism was used to evaluate the ideological, political, and institutional contexts shaping both Soviet and post-independence scholarship.

RESULTS / FINDINGS

The historiographical analysis of post-independence research on the Khorezm archaeological-ethnographic expedition (KAEE) reveals several significant patterns and methodological shifts. First, the study confirms that the expedition's legacy has undergone a gradual transformation from a source-based research tradition into an independent historiographical and conceptual object.

The period 1991–1998 is characterized by the dominance of the Soviet scientific paradigm. During this stage, most scholars accepted the expedition's conclusions as authoritative and continued to rely on the theoretical framework developed by S.P. Tolstov. Critical reinterpretation was limited, and the KAEE was mainly perceived as a repository of reliable empirical data. In the second stage (1998–2016), a clear methodological shift occurred. Researchers began to reassess KAEE materials through new conceptual approaches influenced by national cultural policy, international academic trends, and interdisciplinary perspectives. The expedition's data were no longer treated as static sources, but as interpretive constructs shaped by historical and ideological contexts. The contemporary stage (from 2016 to the present) demonstrates a further expansion of research perspectives. The KAEE is increasingly examined in relation to cultural heritage preservation, tourism development, identity construction, and socio-cultural transformation in the

context of “New Uzbekistan.” At this stage, the expedition is interpreted not only as a scientific project, but also as a cultural and institutional phenomenon

DISCUSSION

Although historiography on the activities and scholarly legacy of the Khorezm archaeological-ethnographic expedition (KAEE) began to develop during the Soviet period, the comprehensive study of the expedition as an independent historiographical object became particularly active after the independence of Uzbekistan. Research produced in the post-independence period has been aimed not only at utilizing the expedition’s findings, but also at reassessing its role as a scientific school, its methodological approaches, and its historical significance. This study conditionally divides the post-independence research on the legacy of the Khorezm Archaeological-ethnographic expedition into three stages in order to identify the evolution of scholarly approaches and key methodological turning points:

1991-1998 – the formative stage of ethnographic historiography;

1998-2016 – the stage of reinterpreting expedition materials through new conceptual approaches;

from 2016 to the present – the stage of examining the expedition’s legacy in conjunction with issues of cultural heritage preservation, tourism, and national identity in the context of “New Uzbekistan.”

This classification is provisional and serves to systematize and analyze the scientific and paradigmatic shifts that have occurred in the historiography of the expedition.

The Appropriation of the Khorezm Expedition Legacy (1991-1998)

After Uzbekistan gained independence, an urgent need emerged to re-examine national history, ethnogenetic processes, and cultural heritage free from Soviet ideological constraints. Research produced in this historical context, while partially continuing Soviet scholarly traditions, was at the same time oriented toward reinterpreting the materials of the Khorezm Archaeological-ethnographic expedition (KAEE) within a new socio-political environment.

During this period, leading historians and ethnographers such as K. Shoniyozov, A. Askarov, and I. Jabborov widely drew upon KAEE findings in their studies of the origin of the Uzbek people, ancient statehood, ethnic formation, and cultural development. Their works were strongly influenced by the concepts developed by S.P. Tolstov, particularly his interpretation of the Khorezm oasis as a crossroads of ancient sedentary and semi-nomadic cultures and as a center of irrigated agricultural civilization, as well as his approach to viewing ancient Khorezm within the broader context of regional historical processes. At the same time, elements of Soviet-era ideological stereotypes can still be observed to have persisted by inertia in these studies.

In 1991-1993, contemporary ethnocultural processes in Karakalpakstan also attracted the attention of local scholars. One of the earliest studies directly based on KAEE materials was N.A. Tleubergenova’s dissertation, *Traditional Dwellings of the Karakalpaks in the Nineteenth and Early Twentieth Centuries*. The study analyzes the material culture of the Karakalpak people yurts (black tents), auxiliary buildings, housing structures and decorations, and their social functions on the basis of archival sources, KAEE field data, and museum collections, with particular attention to the conclusions of T.A. Zhdanko, S.K. Kamalov, R.K. Kosbergenov, and U.Kh. Shalekenov.

R.S. Kamalova’s dissertation, *Traditional Beliefs in the Family and Household Rituals of the Karakalpaks*, is devoted to the spiritual culture of the Karakalpak people, focusing on religious concepts and syncretic elements in ritual practices. Drawing on the works of S.P. Tolstov, T.A. Zhdanko, B.V. Andrianov, S.K. Kamalov, L.S. Tolstova, U.Kh. Shalekenov, R.K. Kosbergenov,

G.P. Snesaryov, Kh. Yesbergenov, and N.P. Lobacheva, the author analyzes ancient beliefs associated with birth, marriage, and funerary rites and their synthesis with Islamic and pre-Islamic traditions. This approach constitutes an important historiographical source for understanding processes of ethnocultural identification and religious syncretism among the Karakalpaks.

At this stage, Kh. Yesbergenov's article "Chilpik" is of particular scholarly significance. Based on field ethnographic observations and available archaeological data, the author examines the Chilpik monument located on the right bank of the Amu Darya. The concept proposed by S.P. Tolstov, interpreting Chilpik as a dakhma, was later archaeologically confirmed by Yu.P. Manylov. Nevertheless, as a scholarly hypothesis, Yesbergenov suggested that the monument may have functioned as a Zoroastrian sanctuary in the late first millennium BCE to the first centuries CE, thereby attempting to reveal its broader religious and philosophical meaning.

The studies of T.Kh. Yesbergenova on Karakalpak social life and cultural traditions also played an important role in the process of reappropriating the KAEE legacy. She analyzed folk pedagogy, labor education, and age- and gender-based divisions of labor, reinterpreting field materials collected by L.S. Tolstova, U.Kh. Shalekenov, G.P. Snesaryov, Kh. Yesbergenov, and N.P. Lobacheva from a contemporary perspective.

In 1997, on the occasion of the 60th anniversary of the KAEE and the 90th anniversary of S.P. Tolstov's birth, a series of articles by V.A. Tishkov, Yu.A. Rapoport, M.A. Itina, E.E. Nerazik, Yu.I. Semenov, and other scholars were published in the journal *Etnograficheskoe Obozrenie*. These publications represent important historiographical sources illuminating Tolstov's scholarly activity, the formation of the expedition, its work during the war years, and its role in Soviet ethnography. Overall, studies produced between 1991 and 1998 reflect the formative stage of ethnographic historiography in the early years of Uzbekistan's independence. During this period, the KAEE legacy was largely interpreted within the inertia of the Soviet scientific school, although influenced by the new socio-political context. Tolstov's concepts were mainly continued, the expedition's results were often accepted as "ready-made scientific achievements," and a critical approach was only beginning to emerge.

The Re-conceptualization of the Khorezm Expedition Legacy (1998–2016)

In July 1998, the meeting of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, with leading historians marked the beginning of a new stage in historical scholarship. At this meeting, particular emphasis was placed on the necessity of studying the ethnogenesis, ethnic history, statehood, and cultural heritage of the Uzbek people free from Soviet ideological frameworks and on the basis of modern scholarly approaches. Consequently, a growing tendency emerged to reassess the materials of the Khorezm archaeological-ethnographic expedition (KAEE) and to employ them as an active scholarly source in the process of rewriting national history.

This process was also closely linked with initiatives of UNESCO and the Government of Uzbekistan. In particular, the commemorations of the 2500th anniversary of Khiva (1997), the 800th anniversary of the birth of Jaloliddin Manguberdi (1999), and the 2700th anniversary of the Avesta (2001) significantly increased attention to the historical and cultural heritage of the Khorezm oasis. These events created a favorable political and academic environment for the renewed study of KAEE materials. At this stage, the KAEE legacy was extensively reinterpreted by scholars working in various fields. Among them were M.M. Is'hoqov, I.M. Jabborov, Z.I. Kurbanova, A.Kh. Doniyorov and others.

During this period, Professor M.M. Is'hoqov made a significant contribution by reinterpreting KAEE materials within the context of the Avesta and the history of Zoroastrianism.

While not rejecting S.P. Tolstov's concept of Khorezm as the homeland of Zoroastrianism, he deepened it through new archaeological and philological data. He also characterized Tolstov as a "discoverer and pioneer researcher" in the study of ancient Khorezmian writing. This approach made it possible to consider the KAEE legacy within the broader framework of written culture and civilizational development.

In 2007, an international conference in Urgench dedicated to the 100th anniversary of S.P. Tolstov and the symposium "The Aral Region – A Crossroads of Cultures" held in Nukus further intensified scholarly interest in the KAEE. In their presentations, Academician S.K. Kamalov and Professor I.M. Jabborov highlighted the stages in the formation of Tolstov's scientific school and the expedition's role in the study of regional history. Articles published in the special issues of the journal *History of Uzbekistan* (2007) by Yu. Buryakov, M. Filanovich, A.S. Sagdullayev, U. Abdullayev, A. Asqarov, and S. Baratov recognized Tolstov's legacy as a major scholarly achievement, while simultaneously reassessing some of his theoretical and chronological positions in light of modern archaeological findings. In particular, A.S. Sagdullayev and U. Abdullayev highly evaluated Tolstov's contribution to the study of early statehood, socio-economic structures, and ancient societies through the comprehensive use of archaeological sources, while emphasizing the need to revise certain concepts.

At the same time, subsequent studies enriched Tolstov's ideas on the formation of statehood in Khorezm, the development of ancient cities, and Bronze Age migration processes with new archaeological evidence. The Kozalikir site, the concept of "living walls," and the theory of "Greater Khorezm" have been reassessed by contemporary researchers. Nevertheless, Tolstov's field research methodology and his role in establishing an archaeological school continue to retain their scholarly significance. Particular attention in this stage should be given to the works of A.Kh. Doniyorov, who analyzed the development of ethnography in Uzbekistan in the twentieth century and evaluated the KAEE as a stage of methodological renewal. His textbook *The Khorezm Archaeological-ethnographic expedition in Uzbek Ethnography* provides a general overview of the expedition's formation and major research and serves as a conceptual foundation for subsequent studies.

The studies of Z.I. Kurbanova systematically examine the activities of the expedition's "ethnographic research groups." Using the photo albums of A.L. Melkov, she reveals the importance of the expedition as a visual-ethnographic source and substantiates the decisive role of the KAEE in the study of Karakalpak culture. As a result, the expedition is interpreted as a key stage in the formation of the Central Asian, particularly Karakalpak, ethnographic school.

The works of Russian historians I.A. Arzhantseva and I.A. Alimov introduced a critical theoretical framework into the historiography of the KAEE. I.A. Arzhantseva interprets the expedition as part of the system of "imperial archaeology," thereby revealing the political context of Soviet scholarly activity, and proposes a three-stage periodization of the expedition's internal evolution. The photo-album *Buried Civilizations* (2013) is another important source that presents the expedition within the contexts of scientific school formation, biographical memory, and heritage politics.

I.A. Alimov critically analyzes the figure of S.P. Tolstov as a complex scientific leader shaped within the Soviet political-academic system, emphasizing the need to view him not as a "legendary personality," but as a product of historical processes. Nevertheless, in most of these studies the expedition was addressed mainly within the context of specific themes, and it was not yet sufficiently analyzed as a complex historical and scholarly phenomenon. Therefore, this

dissertation aims to examine the “Khorezm Expedition Phenomenon” as an independent scientific school under the leadership of S.P. Tolstov, within the broader context of Soviet and post-Soviet scholarly and political processes.

From 2016 to the Present: New Approaches to the Khorezm Expedition Legacy in the Era of “New Uzbekistan”. Since 2016, large-scale reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan have made science, the preservation of historical and cultural heritage, the strengthening of national identity, and the development of tourism key priorities of state policy. This process has accelerated scholarly freedom, openness, and conceptual renewal in ethnology and historiography. As a result, the study of the legacy of the Khorezm Archaeological-ethnographic expedition (KAEE) has entered a new stage.

Dissertations and monographs produced during this period are distinguished by their reinterpretation of KAEE materials through modern theoretical frameworks, including the concepts of “heritage,” “identity,” “transformation,” “ethno-integration,” and “ethno-tourism”. I.B. Salaev studies housing construction culture in the Khorezm oasis, while D.Q. Turenliyazova examines Karakalpak handicrafts within the framework of modern ethno-tourism. In these works, the KAEE legacy functions as a historiographical bridge linking classical Soviet ethnography with contemporary cultural policy and economic models.

Fundamental works devoted directly to the history of the expedition also belong to this period. I.A. Arzhantseva’s album (2016) introduced the KAEE archives into scholarly circulation for the first time in a comprehensive manner. The memoir collection on T.A. Zhdanko published in 2021 sheds light on the expedition’s internal life and the spirit of its scientific school. Z.I. Kurbanova’s 2020 monograph substantiated the KAEE as the foundation of Karakalpak ethnographic scholarship. The book *In Search of the Secrets of the Past* (2024) by U. Bekmuhammad and S. Matkarimova evaluates the KAEE as a regional and international scientific school.

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Overall, during this stage the legacy of the Khorezm archaeological-ethnographic expedition (KAEE) developed along two major and interconnected directions. The first direction is represented by studies that reinterpret the expedition’s field materials through modern theoretical and conceptual frameworks. In these works, classical ethnographic and archaeological data are no longer treated merely as descriptive sources, but are analyzed within broader perspectives such as cultural heritage studies, identity theory, social transformation, ethno-integration, and ethno-tourism. This approach allows scholars to link historical materials with contemporary social, political, and cultural processes, thereby demonstrating the continued relevance of the KAEE in modern academic and public discourse.

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